

An alternative procedure to IEC-61853-2 standard for measuring the incidence angle modifier of PV modules

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Relative measurement method for IAM curves in PV modules eliminates solar tracker requirement, enabling simplified field characterization.
- High repeatability and low uncertainty are achieved across full IAM- incidence angle range.
- This methodology enables in-field IAM testing, which is particularly valuable for investigating combined effects of soiling and incidence angle on PV performance.
- Tracking and static simulations reveal a 1.6%–2.6% increase in AAL with 2% soiling compared to clean modules, which reduces the energy performance by 2%–3%.
- This work demonstrates that even low levels of soiling have a notable impact on energy performance estimates.

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ABSTRACT

The Incidence Angle Modifier (*IAM*) testing methods prescribed in IEC-61853-2 face two key difficulties. They require an accurate tracker, and the results are sensitive to errors in irradiance measurements. Consequence of such difficulties is that *IAM* measurements remain a matter for few specialized laboratories and discrepancies between their results have been observed. This paper proposes an alternative method based on comparing the angular response of the module under test with that of a reference module, understood as a module whose *IAM* curve is previously well known (i.e., a module covered by bare glass, whose *IAM* curve is well described by the Fresnel laws). Both modules are placed coplanar on a static surface positioned so that the θ range of interest for *IAM* coincides with the best irradiance conditions. A measuring campaign performed on a commercial PV module with AR coated glass has shown very good repeatability. Standard uncertainty is 1.8% and 2.2% for $\theta \leq 70^\circ$ and $\theta > 70^\circ$, respectively. The use of the reference module translates into low sensitivity to irradiance errors, which allows using irradiance instrumentation alternatives that do not require either pyrheliometers or shadow band pyranometers. Allows in-field testing, attractive for studying the impact of soiling on *IAM*. Simulations for tracking and static configurations, with modules having a normal soiling ratio of 2%, result in Annual Angular Losses (AAL) values of 1.6%–2.6% respectively, larger than the results for similar clean modules. Thus, the final energy yield is reduced by 2%–3%, showing that even low soiling levels noticeably affect the energy yield estimations.

1. Introduction

The Incidence Angle Modifier (*IAM*) is defined as an angular function that quantifies the fraction of direct sunlight that is transmitted through the surface of a PV module. This function depends on the angle of incidence (θ), which is the angle between the normal of the module surface and the direction of the incoming light. When this angle, the reflected direct irradiance (inside the module) also increases and the *IAM* value

decreases consequently. Specifically,

$$IAM(\theta) = \frac{T(\theta)}{T(0)} \quad (1)$$

where T denotes the transmission coefficient, i.e., the fraction of the incident irradiance that is transmitted through the cover and reaches the solar cells.

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Nomenclature

IAM Incidence Angle Modifier
 θ Angle of incidence
T Transmission coefficient
 PV Photovoltaic
 AAL Annual Angular Losses
 B_n Direct Normal Irradiance
B In-plane direct irradiance
 $B_{clearsky(n)}$ Simulated direct irradiance for a clear sky
 G_n Global Normal Irradiance
D(0) Horizontal diffuse irradiance
D In-plane diffuse irradiance
 D_n Diffuse normal irradiance
 β Tilt of module
 AR Anti reflective
n Refractive index
 MUT Module Under Test
 MRE Module of Reference
 α_s Azimuth of the Sun
 θ_{ZS} Zenith angle of the Sun
 α Azimuth of the setup
G Global in-plane irradiance
 G_{efa} Global effective irradiance in-plane

TSH True Solar time in Hours
 I_{sc} Short-circuit current
 F_D^{IAM} Correction factor for the diffuse component
 $R_{ISC}(\theta)$ Ratio of I_{sc} between modules
 $NR_{ISC}(\theta)$ Normalized ratio of I_{sc}
 σ Standard deviation
 c_i Sensitivity coefficient
 a_r Dimensionless parameter of the Martín-Ruiz Model
 NSR Normal Soiling Ratio
u Uncertainty
 CV Coefficient of Variation
 EDC Energy yield in DC
 GCR Ground Coverage Ratio
 TMY Typical Meteorological Year

Superscripts

* At Standard Test Conditions
F Final
C Clean
S Soil

Subscripts

T Test
R Reference
a Annual

Optical losses due to *IAM* can occur in perfectly clean PV modules, as well as in dirty modules. In the former, optical losses occur in the continuous succession of homogeneous layers with different thicknesses and optical properties. In the latter, additional losses associated with soiling occur due to the volumetric properties of dust when it is deposited on the PV module [1–3]. Depending on the geometry of PV array and the solar radiation and the degree of dirtiness the Annual Angular Losses (AAL), which compare the difference between the calculated energy produced considering the *IAM* and without considering *IAM* over the course of a year. These values of AAL are between 1% and 5%; this difference is significant enough to warrant the measurement of the *IAM*.

Normalized *IAM* measurements are prescribed in IEC-61853-2 standard [4], which specifies either indoor (sun simulator) or outdoor (real sun) methods. In both cases, the PV device under test (an entire module, a single cell. . .) is rotated by means of an accurate tracker device to vary the incident angle of the in-plane irradiance with accuracy better than $\pm 1^\circ$. At the same time, the short-circuit current of the device, $I_{sc}(\theta)$, is recorded. Then, assuming perfectly collimated and constant irradiance throughout the process, and that the temperature of the measured device remains constant,

$$IAM(\theta) = \frac{I_{SC}(\theta)}{I_{SC}(0) \cos(\theta)} \tag{2}$$

The main difficulties in both methods are rooted in the angular distribution and the homogeneity of in-plane irradiance. Indoor methods can suffer from high irradiance volume non-uniformity when measuring entire PV modules. Light collimators or large tunnels (> 8 m) are effective but expensive solutions. An alternative consists of restricting the electrical measurement to an individual cell (or string) [5]. However, that requires accessing the interior of the module, breaking the encapsulation somehow to electrically isolate the cell, which is very difficult in glass–glass modules that are very common today.

An indoor method different from the IEC-61853-2 one has been recently proposed and applied to only single-cell minimodules [6]. Outdoor methods assure irradiance homogeneity, but cannot avoid some diffuse component, even when testing around midday on clear days. The experience with outdoor methods began as early as 1997 [7]. It is

necessary to accurately measure this diffuse component in order to discount its effects on the short-circuit current of the tested module. This is extremely sensitive to instrument precision, where the largest contribution is the diffuse irradiance sensor [8,9], which even motivated the development of specific pyranometers for this measurement [9]. Looking to minimize the effect of such diffuse irradiance, IEC-61853-2 requires the test to be carried out on very clear days. The ratio between Direct Normal Irradiance, B_n , and Global Normal Irradiance, G_n , must be larger than 85%. Mounting errors and inaccurate measurement of θ have also been identified as a source of errors in *IAM* testing [10].

To summarize, adhering to IEC-61853-2 for *IAM* testing requires overcoming significant difficulties. In any case, an expensive tracker device is required for determining the module position with accuracy better than $\pm 1^\circ$. Moreover, in case of indoor testing, that requires either an expensive solar simulator or breaking the module encapsulation for collimating the light and, in case of outdoor testing, that requires highly accurate *B* and *D* measurements for adequate consideration of in-plane diffuse radiation. An undesired consequence of such difficulties is that *IAM* measurements remain a matter of few specialized laboratories around the world. Besides, large discrepancies between results from different laboratories have been observed. That has raised suspicions about *IAM* accuracy. For example, PVsyst says “we have received many measurements which are contradictory. . . and we don’t accept them for the database if they are too different than the Fresnel laws. . . . since 2017 (version 6.53) we don’t accept outdoor *IAM* measurements for new modules of the PVsyst databases. Only the indoor data are retained, as far as they are not too high” [10]. On the same lines, [8] note that the variation in *IAM* losses for the same module—depending on *IAM* profiles from different sources—is often greater than the performance differences observed between distinct modules when using a single source. This way, when energy yield comparison exercises are performed for selecting between different modules for a PV plant, the use of one or another *IAM* source could award an artificially inflated advantage of 0.5%, in terms of annual energy yield, enough to tip the decision towards one module or another.

These suspicions, together with the widely recognized validity of Fresnel laws, even lead to doubts about the convenience of measuring

IAM. In fact, the IEC-61853-2 states that “For modules with a flat uncoated front glass plate, the *IAM* test does not need to be performed, rather, the data of a flat glass air interface can be used”. Further validation studies support this statement [11]. And the same could be true for modules with AR-coated glass. A white paper published by PVEL concerning these modules states that: “The results of the *IAM* test have a striking level of good agreement with the theoretical Fresnel calculations for glass with AR coating” [12]. However, we think that *IAM* measurements are still interesting, not only for studying the angular behavior of the diverse PV module technologies but also for studying the effect of soiling on *IAM*.

We have no direct experience with either of two IEC-61853 *IAM* testing procedures. However, we have extensive experience in outdoor measurements of PV modules [13–15], in which we have learned that generally great accuracy can be achieved by performing relative measurements, that is, measurements whose result is established in relation to a similar measurement carried out on a similar device well known in advance. That led us to try measuring the *IAM* of a PV module by comparing its angular response with that corresponding to a reference module, understood as a module whose *IAM* curve is previously well known. This idea was suggested many years ago in 2004 [16], but as far as we know it has never been implemented until now. We have done it using as reference a PV module covered by bare glass, whose *IAM* curve is well described by the Fresnel laws corresponding to a refraction index $n = 1.526$. For that, both modules, respectively referred to as MUT (Module Under Test) and MRE (Module of Reference), are arranged coplanarly on a static surface, thus avoiding the need for a tracker; letting the Sun move to cover the interesting range of angles of incidence (40° – 80°). In line with the norm, the position of this surface must be known with accuracy better than $\pm 1^\circ$. On the other hand, the use of a reference module greatly reduces the sensitivity of *IAM* results to the accuracy of irradiance components. That opens the door to *IAM* testing being performed in conventional laboratories, and even to *IAM* testing being performed in the field, taking advantage of the fact that the orientation of PV array surfaces tends to be carefully determined during the construction of utility-scale PV plants. That represents an appealing alternative for measuring dust impact on *IAM* and *IAM* in aged modules, which represent open questions today.

Fig. 1 helps to understand the fundamental basis of the here proposed method: instead of measuring directly the *IAM* curve of the module under test (in red line), it is determined from the observation of its difference (shaded area) with the *IAM* of the reference module (in green), which is assumed to be well known beforehand.

Fig. 1. The basic principle of the proposed *IAM* testing methodology consists of determining the *IAM* curve by observing the difference between the *IAM* behavior of the module under test and a reference module, whose *IAM* curve is well known beforehand.

This paper presents the details of the experimental set-up implemented at the IES-UPM terrace in Madrid; discloses the procedure for deriving the experimental *IAM* curves; estimates the associated uncertainty, highlighting the superior stability of the derived *IAM* results in the face of potential irradiance errors when compared to the IEC-61853 procedures; and presents some results for both perfectly clean and soiled PV modules.

2. *IAM* testing procedure

The procedure consists of recording the short-circuit currents of a MUT and an MRE, both coplanar on a static surface, and letting the Sun move to cover the interesting range of angles of incidence. Simultaneously, the direct normal irradiance, B_n and horizontal diffuse irradiance, $D(0)$ are also recorded from the pyrheliometer and the shadow-ball pyranometer of the existing meteorological station, as shown in Fig. 2. Then, corresponding in-plane direct irradiance, B , and in-plane diffuse irradiance, D , are derived. It is important to look for the coincidence of the θ range of interest for *IAM*, let us say $40^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$, with the best irradiance conditions, i.e., the B_n/G_n highest ratio greater than 85%, which corresponds to a normal incidence on the module with diffuse component contribution of less than 15%. For this reason, the testing surface is facing near East (with an orientation of 114° from the astronomical north in a retrograde direction) and tilted 40° . Finally, the ground in front of the modules is covered by a very low reflectivity material (we used black-painted artificial grass), so that the ground reflected irradiance can be disregarded. Fig. 2 shows our experimental set-up at the IES-UPM terrace in Madrid.

For given azimuth, α , and tilt, β , of the testing surface, θ is calculated as,

$$\theta = \arccos(\cos \beta \cos \alpha_S + \sin \beta \sin \theta_{ZS} \cos(\alpha_S - \alpha)) \quad (3)$$

where α_S and θ_{ZS} are, respectively, the azimuth and zenith angles of the Sun which, in turn, are derived from time (hour and day) and latitude. Corresponding equations are found in basic solar radiation texts. Due to the high angular sensitivity of *IAM*, θ and, therefore, α and β must be known with great accuracy. We have used an advanced topographic procedure leading to $\pm 0.2^\circ$ in determining α , and a standard inclinometer with $\pm 0.1^\circ$ in β . This way, resulting accuracy in θ is better than $\pm 0.5^\circ$ (well below the limit prescribed in ISO/IEC, Guide 98-3 [17]).

For explanation purposes, Fig. 3 shows the evolution along an equinox clear day of θ and D_n/G_n ratio corresponding to the proposed

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for *IAM* testing. Left) setup with two coplanar modules (MRE and MUT) with a tilted angle of 40° . Right) meteorological station with a pyrheliometer for B_n and a pyranometer with a shadow ball for $D(0)$. G is also measured with a pyranometer mounted on the module test plane and close to it.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the configuration of a module with 40° tilt in Madrid, Spain, with SOUTH orientation ($\alpha = 0^\circ$), and a module with EAST orientation ($\alpha = -90^\circ$). Evolution of the angle of incidence θ (red dashed/continuous line for SOUTH/EAST orientation, respectively) and the simulated direct irradiance for a clear sky $B_{\text{clearsky}(n)}$ (black continuous line); the true solar time is expressed in hours (TSH), where zero corresponds to solar noon. The grey band is intended to emphasize the analysis for an EAST orientated structure where the maximum irradiance values effectively correspond to the most IAM sensitive angles.

surface, and to an equally tilted but south-oriented surface. The outstanding fact is that the East orientation ensures that, from 40 to 80°, the θ range of IAM interest coincides with the clearest sky conditions.

The method for obtaining D deserves further comment. Assuming an isotropic sky model developed by [18,19], we calculate D as

$$D = \frac{D(0)(1 + \cos \beta)}{2} \quad (4)$$

But other instrumentation possibilities exist. We have tried using the global in-plane irradiance, G , as measured by a pyranometer mounted on the testing surface (visible in Fig. 2). Then:

$$D = G - B_n \cos \theta \quad (5)$$

However, previous research has indicated [20] that pyranometers fail to display an ideal cosine response to the angle of incidence and the variation can exceed 10% for angles larger than 50°. The undesired consequence is that D obtained from Eq. (5) systematically tends to be lower than real. We have even obtained negative D values, which are physically meaningless and lead us to opt for standard B_n and $D(0)$ measurements. Later, we will see that the use of the MRE makes IAM results scarcely sensitive to B_n and D , which opens the door to other instrumentation possibilities that do not require a pyrheliometer. We will return to this matter in Section 4.4.

2.1. Theoretical background

Leaving apart the effect of spectrum and temperature, the short-circuit current of a PV module, I_{sc} , is given by:

$$I_{sc} = \frac{I_{sc}^*}{G^*} [B_n \cos \theta \cdot IAM(\theta) + D \cdot F_D^{IAM}] \quad (6)$$

where the superscript * stands for Standard Test Conditions ($G^* = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$) and F_D^{IAM} is the IAM correction factor for the diffuse component, which results from integrating $IAM(\theta)$ across the angular range of the sky visible to the module. The reader interested in this integral can consult [21,22]. Here it was assumed that, for a given $IAM(\theta)$, its

Fig. 4. F_D^{IAM} values calculated using the Fresnel laws.

solution depends only on β . Fig. 4 shows F_D^{IAM} , assuming that the first is properly described by the application of the Fresnel Laws to the air–module interface, characterized by a certain n . It is worth noting that, for a given β , the variation of F_D^{IAM} with n is small. For example, for $\beta = 50^\circ$, $F_D^{IAM}(n = 1.526) = 0.96$ and $F_D^{IAM}(n = 1.2) = 0.97$. Similar results are obtained with Fresnel IAM models and with IAM descriptions by means of a set of experimental values such as those found in the pan.files promoted by PVsyst.

2.2. IAM derivation

The IAM derivation procedure is based on the observed ratio between the I_{sc} of tested and the reference modules, which is given by:

$$R_{I_{sc}}(\theta) = \frac{I_{sc,T}^*}{I_{sc,R}^*} \cdot \frac{B_n \cos \theta \cdot IAM_T(\theta) + D \cdot F_{D,T}^{IAM}}{B_n \cos \theta \cdot IAM_R(\theta) + D \cdot F_{D,R}^{IAM}} \quad (7)$$

where the subscripts T and R stand for tested and reference, respectively. Note that for low θ , let us say $\theta \leq 30^\circ$, $IAM_T(\theta) \approx IAM_R(\theta) \approx 1$. Then, assuming $F_{D,T}^{IAM} \approx F_{D,R}^{IAM}$

$$R_{I_{sc}}(\theta \leq 30^\circ) = \frac{I_{sc,T}^*}{I_{sc,R}^*} \quad (8)$$

and defining

$$NR_{I_{sc}}(\theta) = \frac{R_{I_{sc}}(\theta)}{R_{I_{sc}}(\theta \leq 30^\circ)} \quad (9)$$

where the denominator corresponds to the maximum value of I_{sc} over the course of a day.

$IAM_T(\theta)$ is calculated as

$$IAM_T(\theta) = \frac{NR_{I_{sc}}(\theta) B_n \cos \theta - IAM_R(\theta) + D \cdot F_{D,R}^{IAM} [NR_{I_{sc}}(\theta) - 1]}{B_n \cos \theta} \quad (10)$$

In principle, once the entire $IAM_T(\theta)$ curve is derived in this way, the value $F_{D,T}^{IAM}$ can be calculated, as commented above, and a successive approximation process can be performed for refining $IAM_T(\theta)$, based on improving the initial supposition for this value. However, our experience is that this is not worthwhile, because the refinement affects only the fourth decimal place, which is outside the expected uncertainty. In this sense, it is worth mentioning that other authors [9,11] rely on the still simpler approximation $F_{D,T}^{IAM} \approx F_{D,R}^{IAM} \approx 1$ in the outdoor procedures based on IEC 61853–2.

2.3. Data acquisition and filtering

Data is recorded every minute, which allows for obtaining 4 or 5 IAM values for each one-degree interval of θ .

To avoid anomalous data due to rapid variations in irradiance caused by passing clouds, we exclude values that fall outside the 2σ range.

3. Results

3.1. A representative case

As a representative example, Fig. 5 presents the relevant data recorded in an IAM test of a module Meyer Burger BLACK 380, whose frontal cover is an AR-coated glass. This is a clear day, where the figure at the top shows the measured irradiance and current ratio data. At the bottom are the calculated results for θ and irradiance ratios D/G in-plane and D_n/G_n as indicated by the standard. Table 1 gives the corresponding numerical values of the ratio in the range of angles of incidence, demonstrating that measurements were taken under clear weather conditions at all times.

For reference, Table 1 also includes the $IAM(\theta)$ values provided by the manufacturer, which are somewhat more optimistic than ours, but the difference is frankly small. Other intercomparison studies between laboratories [23] indicate that for ranges of $\theta \leq 65^\circ$ the uncertainty is $\pm 2\%$ and for ranges between $70^\circ \leq \theta \leq 85^\circ$ the uncertainty rapidly increases from 2.5% to 23%. However, in our example, the maximum manufacturer-test difference is 3.4%, well below the uncertainty reported in such comparison studies.

This example can help us to delve deeper into the role of the MRE as an error smoother by analyzing what would happen if it were not there. Then, we could still derive $IAM(\theta)$ from Eq. (6), as:

$$IAM(\theta) = \frac{\frac{I_{SC}}{(I_{SC}^*/G^*)} - D \cdot F_D^{IAM}}{B_n \cos \theta} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 5. Representative data collected in one day (28th June 2025) to reconstruct the IAM curve using the proposed relative measurement method. The upper part of figure shows both B_n (green line), G (black line), $D(0)$ and the ratio between the recorded short circuit current of the reference (MRE) and module under test (MUT) along the data acquisition. The lower figure shows the evolution of the θ (blue line). The grey box highlights the incident angle range of interest for IAM, $40^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$. The ratio between diffuse and global components in-plane to the module (orange) and in-plane to the sun (purple) is also plotted.

Table 1

Comparison between the results of the alternative IAM measurement and what the manufacturer indicates in its pan.file listing, in addition to the details of the irradiance variables for each θ .

θ	IAM result	B_n (W/m ²)	D (W/m ²)	Ratio D_n/G_n standard	IAM manufacturer	$\Delta(\%)$	Manuf-Test Test
0	1	862	94	0.100	1	0	
20	1	895	102	0.111	1	0	
40	0.994	897	115	0.126	1	0.6	
60	0.959	829	133	0.149	0.967	0.8	
65	0.929	813	119	0.151	0.950	2.2	
70	0.88	805	138	0.153	0.91	3.4	
75	0.806	791	135	0.149	0.829	2.8	
80	0.666	767	132	0.146	0.683	2.6	
90	0	732	150	0.163	0	0	

Table 2

Exercise involving a 10% variation in irradiance values and calculation of sensitivity coefficients in both measurement methods.

B_n (W/m ²)	D (W/m ²)	IAM(65°)	
		Eq. (10)	Eq. (11)
Observed at the test			
813	119	0.929	0.728
Supposed			
813 + 10% of B_n	=	0.92731	0.66143
813 - 10% of B_n	=	0.92817	0.80841
=	119 + 10% of D	0.92812	0.69445
=	119 - 10% of D	0.92727	0.76069
Sensitivity Coefficients			
	c^B (m ² /W)	-5.32×10^{-6}	-9.04×10^{-4}
	c^D (m ² /W)	3.61×10^{-5}	-2.79×10^{-3}
	c^B (Eq11)/ c^B (Eq10)	170	
	c^D (Eq11)/ c^D (Eq10)	-77	

simply by realizing again that $IAM(\theta \leq 30^\circ) = 1$, which allows determining the ratio I_{SC}^*/G^* from the observations at $\theta \leq 30^\circ$. Leaving aside the use of a tracker, this is very similar to the procedure specified in IEC-61853-2. Note that B_n and D appear in both the numerator and denominator of Eq. (10) while they are only in one of the terms in Eq. (11). This has relevant consequences regarding the sensitivity of $IAM(\theta)$ results to errors in irradiance measurements. According to the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty [17], the sensitivity coefficient can be determined by varying the input variable while holding all other variables fixed, and measuring the resulting change in the output variable. This way, the sensitivity coefficients for the errors in B_n and D are given by

$$c^B = \frac{\Delta IAM}{\Delta B_n} \quad \text{and} \quad c^D = \frac{\Delta IAM}{\Delta D} \quad (12)$$

Table 2 presents the results of calculating the sensitivity coefficients of $IAM(\theta)$ to B_n and D by changing the experimental values observed for $\theta = 65^\circ$. This exercise shows that the proposed method is more sensitive to diffuse irradiance than to direct irradiance, according to the values obtained for the sensitivity coefficients, c^B and c^D . The outstanding result is that these sensitivity coefficients are much smaller when using the MRE (Eq. (10)) (170 times for B_n and 70 times for D). A nice consequence is opening the door to the use of simple instrumentation for measuring irradiance, even without a pyrheliometer. We will return to this matter in Section 4.4.

4. Accuracy

To determine the accuracy of our proposed method in this work, the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement [17], defines and establishes a difference between type A and type B uncertainty. The former is estimated using statistical methods such as standard deviation of a series of repetitions. The latter is calculated from the intrinsic uncertainty and calibration of the measuring instruments.

4.1. Uncertainty type A

To quantify type A uncertainties, a dedicated testing campaign was conducted over a same module Meyer Burger BLACK 380 over 15 clear days. Table 3 shows the resulting average, standard deviation and coefficient of variation, CV, defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean, for different θ . The corresponding sky condition, again in terms of D_n/G_n is also given in terms of average and standard deviation. The following comments apply:

- The high repeatability of IAM results is noticeable. The CV is below 1.5% for all the range $\theta \leq 70^\circ$, and below 2% for all the range $\theta > 70^\circ$. We can use these values as a conservative estimation of uncertainty.

Table 3

Data from the measurement campaign for 15 clear days. Maximum and minimum values obtained across the entire set of measurements.

θ°	IAM(θ)			Irradiance Relationship D/G			
	Mean	Standard deviation	CV (%)	Max	Min	Mean	Standard deviation
0	1	0	0	1	1	0.140	0.037
20	1	0	0	1	1	0.137	0.031
40	0.996	0.002	0.2	0.998	0.990	0.139	0.033
60	0.962	0.007	0.7	0.972	0.947	0.143	0.034
65	0.939	0.008	0.9	0.952	0.930	0.150	0.044
70	0.896	0.012	1.3	0.924	0.883	0.147	0.043
75	0.817	0.017	2.1	0.858	0.802	0.139	0.034
80	0.674	0.012	1.8	0.687	0.633	0.131	0.028
90	0	0	0	0	0	0.133	0.030

Fig. 6. For each θ of interest provided by the manufacturer, it has been represented with both the mean value shown as horizontal blue bar and the standard deviation shown as a vertical blue bar calculated over 15 experimental days.

- That is:

$$u_A(\theta \leq 70^\circ) = 1.5\% \quad \text{and} \quad u_A(\theta > 70^\circ) = 2\% \quad (13)$$

From Fig. 6, a higher discrepancy can be observed for higher θ values. This is also in line with the results of [23] where higher measurement uncertainty was obtained for $\theta > 85^\circ$.

Note that the measurement campaign is limited to clear days, as the results we have obtained for days with a D/G ratio exceeding 0.15 exhibit deviations in the first and second decimal places of the IAM , which suggests that the method is more accurate under clear conditions.

4.2. Uncertainty type B

Above, we have developed an exercise showing that the MRE allows us to greatly smooth the impact of irradiance errors, to the point that they can be disregarded. Hence, the main remaining sources of Type B uncertainty are the position of the testing surface, for which we assume an error of 0.5° (Section 2); the $IAM(\theta)$ calibration of the MRE, for which we assume the Fresnel law for $n = 1.526$; and the instrumentation for reading the I_{SC} of the MUT and MRE. Note that both $IAM_R(\theta)$ and $NR_{I_{SC}}(\theta)$ appear in the numerator but not in the denominator of Eq. (10).

We use good quality current meters with accuracy better than 0.3%. Hence, we estimated that for all the components together, the total type B uncertainty in $IAM(\theta)$ is $u_B = 1\%$.

4.3. Combined and expanded uncertainty

All uncertainty components outlined above are treated as statistically independent. The combined uncertainty is therefore calculated as:

Table 4

PV plant solar climate and simulation outcomes. $G_a(0)$ and $D_a(0)$ annual irradiances, ratio between them, tilt β and GCR.

Country	Latitude	$G_a(0)$ (kWh/m ²)	$\frac{D_a(0)}{G_a(0)}$	β	GCR ($^\circ$)
Spain	39.9	1786	0.32	20	0.5
<i>IAM uncertainty on the annual energy yield</i>					
Annual DC energy E_{DC}^a (kWh/kWp)	with $a_r = 0.174$	with $a_r = 0.136$			
	1520	1539			
<i>Impact of AAL</i>					
G_a (kWh/m ²)	$G_{e,fa}$	$G_{e,fa}$			
2007.9	1940	1968			
AAL %	3.4	2.0			

$$u_C = \sqrt{u_A^2 + u_B^2} \quad (14)$$

That leads to

$$u_C(\theta \leq 70^\circ) = 1.8\% \quad \text{and} \quad u_C(\theta > 70^\circ) = 2.2\% \quad (15)$$

On the other side, the expanded uncertainty at 95% confidence corresponds to a coverage factor of $k = 2$. An interesting way to appreciate the impact of this uncertainty consists of calculating the effective in-plane irradiation, $EDCa$, and annual DC energy yield for the two extreme $IAM(\theta)$ curves resulting from this expanded uncertainty (average $\pm 2u_C$). We have performed corresponding simulation exercises for a static monofacial PV plant located near Madrid and with perfectly clean PV arrays, using SISIFO, free and open-source simulation software created by the Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (IES-UPM) (freely accessible at <https://sisifo.info>). For that, following the suggestions of [4], we first described the $IAM(\theta)$ curves by means of the Martin-Ruiz model and their corresponding a_r coefficient [21,24–26]. Table 4 shows the relevant data and results of these exercises.

To quantify the annual energy losses due to angular effects, we express them in percentage terms. They are calculated as the percentage difference between the irradiance in the plane of the arrays, G_a , and the effective irradiance, $G_{e,fa}$, which is calculated as a result of the integrated simulation exercise for the entire typical meteorological year, TMY.

4.4. Looking for in-field measurements

In-field measuring of $IAM(\theta)$ is attractive when thinking about studying phenomena like the IAM of soiled modules or the IAM degradation of aged modules.

Typically, the azimuth of the PV arrays of utility-scale PV plants is well determined during the construction phase, so that an inclinometer

Table 5

Comparison of *IAM* relative measurements as function of the θ for two different irradiation instruments: meteorological station and SPN1 advanced pyranometer.

θ (°)	Meteorological station <i>IAM</i>	SPN1 <i>IAM</i>
0	1	1
20	1	1
40	0.996	0.998
60	0.969	0.969
65	0.947	0.946
70	0.905	0.900
75	0.827	0.814
80	0.672	0.660
90	0	0

suffices for properly determining the position of any PV array surface and, in turn, the value of θ at any moment. PV plants with one-axis tracking are particularly appealing, because positions close to the limit rotation angle meet the same requirement as our testing surface: combining the θ range of *IAM* interest with clear sky irradiance conditions. On the other hand, pyrheliometers are not found in the meteorological stations of commercial plants but, knowing the low sensitivity of our *IAM*(θ) results to errors in irradiance (see Section 3.1), we have explored other instrumentation alternatives that do not use a pyrheliometer.

Table 5 shows the *IAM*(θ) results obtained from the irradiances given by the meteorological station and from the irradiances given by a SPN1 (visible in Fig. 7), an advanced pyranometer that simultaneously provides the global and diffuse in-plane irradiances, allowing to deduction of the direct component by subtracting these two values. The experiment was performed on the 9th of April 2025. Both results are consistent to the second decimal place, which confirms the validity of the experiments carried out with this instrument, which is very easy to transport and install in the field.

Then, using only the SPN1, we conducted an experiment to measure the impact of soiling on the *IAM*, using two identical modules: one clean

Fig. 7. SPN1 advanced pyranometer from “Delta-T Devices”. Both global and diffuse in-plane irradiances are explicitly measured with this advanced instrument. Please note that once *G* and *D* are well known, the beam component can be easily obtained from the closure equation Eq. (5).

as a reference and the other soiled after remaining exposed outdoors for 30 days. The Normal Soiling Ratio, NSR, defined as the reduction in transmittance for normal irradiance, has been determined by comparing the ratios between the I_{sc} of both modules for $\theta \leq 30^\circ$ observed the first day (both modules clean) and the day 28th November 2025. The result was $NSR = 2\%$. On the other hand, note that the finally observed *IAM* can be described as the product of two *IAM* functions corresponding, respectively, to the clean module and to the soil. That is:

$$IAM^F = IAM^C \cdot IAM^S \tag{16}$$

where the superscripts F, C and S denote, respectively, final, clean and soil. Fig. 8 shows a perspective of the two modules on the day of the experiment. Fig. 9 and Table 6 present the corresponding results. IAM^F is obtained from Eq. (10) with $IAM_R = IAM^C \cdot IAM^S$ was previously determined as explained above. An annual yield simulation exercise was performed for a static, shadow-free and tilted 20° PV array located near Madrid. Previously, IAM^F and IAM^C have been adjusted to the *IAM* Martin-Ruiz model [21,24–26], as suggested in IEC-61853-2. The resulting model coefficients are $a_r = 0.24$ and $a_r = 0.115$, respectively. These values, together with the TMY of the site have been used as input data for the energy yield simulations performed with SISIFO. The key result is that annual DC energy yield decreases from 1548 to 1455 kWh/kW. That means a reduction of 6%, significantly larger than the 2% corresponding to the NSR. This reveals the need to consider the soil impact in *IAM*. In coherence, we have launched a campaign of IAM^S measurements, on the assumption that IAM^C and IAM^S are fully independent. Reporting on that is left for future work.

Note that in Table 6, losses due to *IAM* for 60° go from 0.978 to 0.953, which means a loss of 2.6%. Therefore, it is not surprising that if

Fig. 8. Side view of the setup with two identical modules LR4-60HIH-375M LONGI solar (similar optical and electrical properties from same manufacturer), one is clean (MRE) and the other exhibits a certain degree of soiling (MUT).

Fig. 9. *IAM* curve distinction between IAM^C (red) and IAM^F (blue).

Table 6
Comparison of *IAM* relative measurements as function of the θ for the two contributions (*IAM^C*, *IAM^F*) and the result of the two components (*IAM^S*).

$\theta(^{\circ})$	<i>IAM^F</i>	<i>IAM^C</i>	<i>IAM^S</i>
0	1	1	1
30	1	1	1
50	0.968	0.991	0.977
60	0.953	0.978	0.974
70	0.840	0.917	0.916
75	0.778	0.855	0.901
80	0.687	0.747	0.919
85	0.515	0.603	0.854
90	0	0	0

Table 7
Summary of the effect of soiling on the annual energy yield (kWh/kWp), effective irradiance (kWh/m²) and the AAL (%) for two different PV plant configurations.

Impact of <i>IAM</i> contributions on the annual energy yield		
Annual energy	<i>IAM^C</i> with $a_r = 0.115$ (NSR = 0%)	<i>IAM^F</i> with $a_r = 0.152$ (NSR = 2%)
Static PV Plant $G_a = 2008$ (kWh/m ²)		
EDC _a (kWh/kWp)	1548	1500
G_{eff} (kWh/m ²)	1981	1892
ΔG_{eff} (%)	4.5	
AAL (%)	1.3	3.9
PV Plant with tracker system (1xp) $G_a = 2372$ (kWh/m ²)		
EDC _a (kWh/kWp)	1791	1754
G_{eff} (kWh/m ²)	2352	2267
ΔG_{eff} (%)	3.6	
AAL (%)	0.9	2.5

we integrate losses due to *IAM* throughout the year, the result is around that percentage range (see Table 7).

In a similar way to Section 4.3, SISIFO simulations with the same PV plant characteristics as the one in Table 7 were carried out to quantify the corresponding energy yield for two *IAM* curves (clean and soiled). In addition, the exercise has been extended to the same PV plant with a solar tracking system. In the following, we note that the annual DC energy yield was reduced by 3.1%. This is because the impact of soiling increased AAL from 1.3% to 3.9%. On the other hand, energy yield for the plant with tracker system decreases by 2.1% due to the increase in AAL from 0.9% to 2.5%.

5. Conclusions

IEC-61853-2 prescribes indoor and outdoor methods for *IAM* testing. In any case, an expensive tracker device is required for determining the module position with accuracy better than $\pm 1^{\circ}$. Moreover, in case of indoor testing, this requires either an expensive solar simulator or breaking the module encapsulation for collimating the light and, in case of outdoor testing, this requires highly accurate *B* and *D* measurements for adequate consideration of the in-plane diffuse radiation. Undesirable consequences of such difficulties are that *IAM* measurements remain a matter of few specialized laboratories around the world, and that large discrepancies between results from different laboratories have been observed. This has raised suspicions about *IAM* accuracy.

This paper proposes an alternative method based on comparing the angular response of the module under test with that corresponding to a reference module, understood as a module whose *IAM* curve is previously well known. Both modules are coplanar placed on a static surface and corresponding I_{SC} values are recorded throughout a day, together with *B* and *D*. This allows avoiding the tracker and relaxing the precision

of the incident irradiance components' measurement. The main requirement is the precise determination of the position of the testing surface. We have implemented this method using as reference a PV module covered by bare glass, whose *IAM* curve is well described by the Fresnel laws corresponding to a refraction index $n = 1.526$. Considering the coincidence of the θ range of interest for *IAM*, let us say $40^{\circ} \leq \theta \leq 80^{\circ}$, with the best irradiance conditions, i.e. the highest B_n/G_n ratio, the testing surface is facing near East (with an orientation of 114° from the astronomical north in a retrograde direction) and tilted 40° . Its azimuth and tilt have been determined with accuracy better than $\pm 0.2^{\circ}$ and $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$, respectively, by means of an advanced topographic procedure and a standard inclinometer. *B* and *D* are obtained from a pyrheliometer and a shadow-ball pyranometer available at the meteorological station of the IES-UPM terrace.

A 15-day measuring campaign performed on a commercial PV module with AR coated glass has shown very good repeatability. The corresponding estimated standard uncertainty ($k = 2$) is 1.8% and 2.2% for $\theta \leq 70^{\circ}$ and $\theta > 70^{\circ}$, respectively. These values are below the uncertainty observed in an intercomparison, where for ranges between $70^{\circ} \leq \theta \leq 85^{\circ}$ the uncertainty rapidly increases from 2.5% to 23%. This campaign has also been used for analyzing the usefulness of the reference module, showing that the sensitivity coefficients of the *IAM* results to errors in irradiance measurements are strongly (up to 200 times) reduced by the use of such module.

Looking for future in-field measurements aimed at studying the *IAM* of soiled modules or the *IAM* degradation of aged modules and knowing the low sensitivity of our *IAM*(θ) results to errors in irradiance (See Section 3.1), we have explored other alternative instrumentation that does not use a pyrheliometer. We have used the SPN1, a pyranometer from "Delta-T Devices" installed on the testing surface that gives values of *G* and *D* (*B* is obtained by subtracting the second from the first). Corresponding *IAM* results are consistent to the second decimal place with the ones derived from the irradiance values given by the pyrheliometer and the shadow-ball pyranometer. Then, using only the SPN1, we conducted an experiment to measure the impact of soiling on the *IAM*, using two identical modules: one clean as a reference and the other soiled, after remaining exposed outdoors for 30 days. The NSR after this exposure was 2%. A further yield simulation exercise shows that the DC energy yield was reduced by 3.1%. This is because the impact of soiling increased AAL from 1.3% to 3.9%. On the other hand, energy yield for the plant with tracker system decreases by 2.1% due to the increase in AAL from 0.9% to 2.5%.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Felipe Ríos-Ledesma: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Laura Barrutia:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Celena Lorenzo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eduardo Lorenzo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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